

Cobots: Human-Robot Collaboration

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Abstract:

Human-Robot Collaboration is a new trend in industrial and service robots as part of the industry 4.0 plan. Robots and the approach are referred as the MRK (Mensch Roboter Kollaboration) in Germany and HRC (Human Robot Collaboration) in English. The primary objective of this novel method is to provide a safe environment for human-robot collaboration. There is a transition period between manual and completely automated manufacturing in which a human worker interacts with a machine. Due to safety concerns, this location has various constraints. Combining human talent and innovation with robot power and speed is necessary to overcome these enduring problems. Human-robot collaboration i.e. Cobots is becoming increasingly crucial in the age of automation and robotization. Only when the operational crew is not present in the machine's workplace is it permitted to operate automatically. Collaborative robotics opens up new avenues for human- machine collaboration. Personnel share the workstation with the robot, which assists him with non-ergonomic, repetitive, painful, or even dangerous procedures. The robot watches its motions with sophisticated sensors in order are not to limit, but more importantly, not to jeopardize, it's human partner. The emphasis in this paper is on the overview of collaborative robots, as well as its impact in the industry.

Keywords: Cobots, Collaborative robot, Human Robot Collaboration, Industry 4.0, Industrial robot

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1. Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemics have underscored the importance of resilient supply chains and effective collaboration between humans and machines within the workplace. Mandated measures like social distancing and periodic closures have compelled businesses to operate with minimal onsite personnel. Despite challenges such as labor shortages, supply chain disruptions, and production hurdles, businesses face continuous pressure to meet evolving customer demands. Integration of human ingenuity and innovation with the efficiency and speed of robots is imperative to surmount these persistent challenges. In this context, human-robot collaboration, known as collaborative robotics or "cobots", is increasingly vital in the era of automation and robotization. Their technology landscape is dynamically adapting to their preferences and behaviors, largely attributed to advancements in artificial intelligence algorithms. Cobots, or collaborative robots, are specifically designed to interact and cooperate with human operators. Particularly in the context of Industry 4.0, industrial cobots are anticipated to play a significant role due to their ability to operate safely and efficiently alongside humans. An exemplary instance is the universally authorized lightweight robot, LBR iiwa, developed by KUKA [1].

The core function of a cobot is to aid machine operators in their tasks, expanding automation opportunities and blurring the boundaries between cobots, traditional robots, and human roles. Initially conceived for direct physical interaction between machines and humans, cobots enable businesses to enhance production, swiftly adapt to evolving consumer preferences, and ensure the well-being of their workforce, clientele, and collaborators. Advancements in cobot technology encompass faster response times, precise movement algorithms, refined orientation abilities, and the capacity to emulate human actions. Notably, the progress in brain-computer interfaces represents an intriguing domain, potentially revolutionizing our interaction with robots.

Accurate decoding and transmission of brain signals to robots could open up entirely novel approaches to collaborative work with robots.

Figure 1: Standing of Human – Robot Collaboration [1]

2. History of Cobots

2.1 Industry 4.0

Industry 4.0 refers to the fourth industrial revolution. Numerous physical and digital technologies work together to bring about this shift. The primary elements of Industry 4.0 that textile sector first recognized center on the use of technology meant to computerize and automate operations, whose primary goals include raising productivity and lowering costs. By improving resource efficiency and productivity, industrial transformation primarily aims to boost businesses' competitiveness. Projects to use augmented reality, 3D printing, and simulation technologies in the textile, clothing, and apparel sectors are still in their infancy. Typically, these projects make use of tools and software designed to build new types of processes, goods, and business models. People see the benefits of Industry 4.0 implementation, such as a 15% reduction in energy usage, a 25% increase in work efficiency, more proactive decision-making, process optimization, and a better balance of work and life. Real-time communication, computer applications, carbon, fibres, health care, and sustainable development are developing and/or unknown sectors of Industry 4.0 in the textile business.

2.2 Robots to Cobots

When it comes to cobots vs. robots in manufacturing, the distinction lies in their purpose and, as a result, the type of duty allocated to these entities. Industrial collaboration robots are generally intended to work alongside humans to enhance human employees' job. They are not self-sufficient, but rather human-powered, and are utilized to boost production and effectiveness by providing extra strength, power, accuracy, and data. The main distinction is that cobots enhance the standard while robots replace them. Aside from that, cobots are simpler to develop and learn. Due to their size and strength, industrial robots are occasionally caged to safeguard employees from accidents. An industrial collaborative robot, on the other hand, may work on things like precise welding or quality assurance in the same plant.

Table 1: Comparison between traditional vs latest cobots [4]

	Traditional Industrial Robots	Latest Cobots
Flexibility	Fixed installation	Flexibly relocated
Price	Profitable (medium-large lot)	Profitable (small lot size)
Interaction	Rare interaction with worker, only if being programmed	Frequent interaction with the worker, even force/ precision assistance

General Motors (GM) introduced robots to operate side by side with people and contribute what each performed best amid industry clamor for better ergonomic working conditions. The eventual product was a class of robots that

could carry a weight in its entirety but required human labour to transport it from one location to another. Since then, the use of cobots in the workplace has increased gradually. The three main jobs that cobots are used for most often include choosing and moving objects from one place to another, handling materials, and assembling. These operations will generate 75% of all cobot income over the next five years. Cobots often increase the chances to use automated processes rather than replacing or competing with robots.

Figure 2: Robot workplace with collaborative robot [1]

3. Balancing between Human and Task benefits

The need to assess the requirements for the implementation of cobots arose from the interest of management in industrial enterprises, which planned to introduce them as part of the expansion of the industrial park. About every job posting in an industrial context emphasizes the need for the employee to be innovative. As of now, the robots have failed to meet this condition. They lack the ingenuity and capacity to devise new and improved techniques. As a result, it is best to see the robot as a genuine coworker who may help to reduce the risk of workplace injuries [4].

There are two types of risk prevention assistance provided during the adoption of the cobot inside industrial processes. ISO (International Organization for Standardization) standards that are applicable are optional and guide the implementation process while avoiding mistakes and waste. Legislation, on the other hand, is binding and must be obeyed exactly as written. In a robotized workplace, safety regulations are defined with the goal of eliminating hazards by designing appropriate equipment, applying safety equipment (e.g., safety buttons or sensors), providing safety and health markings (e.g., warning signs), educating and training employees in production, programmers, and service personnel (training and practical exercises), and using personal protective devices [5].

Cobots are particularly useful when a person is required to be in close proximity to the robots. Person-robot partnerships in which a human instructs the robots, oversees the process, or even learns from the robots are examples of this. As the manufacturing labor matures, the complexity of operations on assembly lines rises, and the labour deficit persists, an increasing number of businesses are turning to collaborative robots, or cobots, to help fill the void.

When it comes to cobots and 5G networks, there is a natural match. Quality of service needs, which vary across time and context - think smart manufacturing - will be one of the major aspects of cobots. They give an example of cobots inside a manufacturing facility in their recent publication, with safety zones assigned to each cobot. A cobot in a facility without people does not require the same level of care as a cobot in close proximity to a person. As a result, in more safety-critical contexts, the cobot requires greater signaling, better bandwidth, lower latency, and faster decision-making capabilities through efficient computing [6].

Robots are already the answer to dangerous jobs, such as working with chemical, carcinogenic and toxic substances. Workers' perceptions of their work with cobots have been influenced by the current scenario, which is characterized by widespread transmission of infectious illnesses on the scale of an epidemic or even a pandemic.

A lot of study is being done to see how robots can mimic human motions and decisions. AI algorithms, on the other hand, have proven to be capable of discovering solutions that are superior to those developed by humans. This has been demonstrated in gaming strategies and design optimization difficulties. I believe it would be really intriguing to employ cobots to make human work more efficient, as well as to collaborate between humans and machines.

3.1 Types of Human Robot Collaboration

- Cobots are increasingly becoming a bigger part of the manufacturing pie, according to Joe Chudy, general manager at ABB Robotics. The dual-arm YuMi, single-arm YuMi, GoFa CRB 15000, and SWIFTI CRB 1100 cobots are available from the Zurich, Switzerland-based Robotics Company.
- The market for collaborative robots is predicted to rise at a CAGR [compound annual growth rate] of 17% between 2020 and 2025, with worldwide cobot sales increasing from an estimated \$700 million in 2019 to over \$1.4 billion by 2025, according to Chudy. [4]
- Japan-based FANUC Robots, widely regarded as one of the world's top industrial robot manufacturers, offers two lines of cobots: the FANUC CR series and the CRX Collaborative Robot Series. Worker training and research into further uses for cobots in production are two notable applications of FANUC's cobot robots.
- Some of the biggest challenges ahead include increasing the amount of weight collaborative robots can move and their range, said Campbell. He mentioned that the payload of the company's No. 1 model was recently boosted the UR10e, to 12.5 kg (27.5 lb.), a 25% increase. Cobots are used in manufacturing to work closely with humans on repetitive, painful or monotonous tasks, freeing humans for decision making and other difficult to program task. [5]

4. Categories of Cobot Scenarios

Categories divide tasks according to the relationship between cobots, operators, work pieces, and processes performed on the work pieces. These categorizations draw a clear line between the different skills required for cobots in different industrial scenarios. This is useful for programmers and researchers trying to set a work/research direction. The categories are [7]:

- Independent: Operators and cobots work independently on separate work pieces for individual manufacturing processes. The collaborative element relies on the coexistence of operators and cobots in the same workspace without fencing or protection. In other words, safety is achieved through the cobot's intrinsic safety and/or additional hardware/software safety elements. Therefore, the cobot are aware of the operator's presence and behave safely.
- Simultaneous: The operator and cobot work on different processes on the same work piece at the same time. There are no time or task dependencies between them. However, cobots must be spatially aware of operators and their task requirements in order to respect the operator's space. Processing work pieces simultaneously minimizes work piece transfer time between cobots and humans, improving productivity and space utilization.
- Sequential: Operator and cobot perform sequential manufacturing processes (P1 and P2) on the same work piece. Between the cobot and the operator there is a time dependency of the process. For example, the cobot treat her P1 of the work piece as input and allow the operator to proceed with her P2 of the work piece. In most cases, cobots are designed to take over tedious processes and improve working conditions for operators.
- Supportive: Operators and cobots work interactively towards the same process on the same work piece. There are dependencies between cobots and operator actions. In other words, you can't do another task without one. Collaborative robots must understand operator intent and task requirements in order to provide appropriate assistance. For example, an operator installs a screw in a toolbox while the cobot hold him. The cobot's role is to physically assist the operator in handling the work piece, improving ergonomics.

Figure 3: Cobots in manufacturing, service, and medical applications [1]

4.1 Cobots Communication

To work in teams and execute tasks smoothly and efficiently, humans rely largely on communication. Orders can be issued, intentions can be conveyed, and questions can be asked and answered. Communication signals are detected, recognized, and mapped to cobot activities. The modelling of the gesture is determined by whether it is static or dynamic. For a pose to be detected as a static gesture, its temporal length needs to exceed a specific threshold. In the case of dynamic gestures, the human pose sequence, sampled at a certain rate, is modelled as a timeseries (such as Hidden Markov Models, Recurrent Neural Network) which is then used for detection. Even with well selected gestures, having to memories and adhere to a predefined set of signals can be intellectually taxing and unintuitive for the operator. Allowing a person to speak with a cobot in his or her own unique manner leads to more effective, natural, and intuitive communication. The cobot can learn needed behaviors and relevant objects, states, and tools by asking the proper questions. Creating a natural language system is difficult since the operator's language use changes dramatically as the task continues [8].

In a collaborative task where only verbal communication is allowed, the frequency of morphemes decreases as the number of task trials increase. This is because individuals naturally begin to release words as they grow acclimated to the activity. They automatically begin to evaluate and accommodate their teammates' requirements without those demands being expressly articulated. As a result, any language model between a human and a cobot should account for changes in human language as the human grows more acclimated to the task. Using multi-modal communication can outperform single mode communication. It can also be redundant, such as a voice and gesture system that responds to the same instruction. Before deciding how to adopt multimodal communication, it is critical to examine whether or not it is required. A gesture would only be required, for example, if numerous things with the same verbal description were in close proximity [9].

After specifying a communication guideline, the permissible communicated signals must be mapped to executable cobot actions, i.e., a signal should be made a command. This can be done manually or through learning. An operator can participate in the signal-action mapping through interactive learning. However, in an industrial setting when insufficient variety in mapping is expected, this might introduce unneeded complexities. This allows the cobot to begin operating on the item before an explicit command is sent. This is particularly useful when the communication channel domain is continuous, such as gaze direction, and requires segmentation before mapping. Thier job can be used to direct and initiate communication only when needed. This increases efficiency and reduces the chance of error and confusion.

After defining the communication policy, you need to map the permitted communication signals to possible cobot actions. In other words, the signal should be a command. This can be done manually or by learning. Programmers manually assign gestures to cobot actions based on task needs. Using interactive learning, operators can play a role in signal-action mapping. Even with well selected gestures, having to memories and adhere to a predefined set of signals can be intellectually taxing and unintuitive for the operator. Allowing a person to speak with a cobot

in his or her own unique manner leads to more effective, natural, and intuitive communication. The cobot can learn needed behaviors and relevant objects, states, and tools by asking the proper questions. Creating a natural language system is difficult since the operator's language use changes dramatically as the task continues.

However, this may present unnecessary complexity in an industrial environment where poor variability in imaging is expected. This helps cobots react to objects before issuing an explicit command. This is especially useful when the communication channel domain is contiguous. Line of sight, segmentation is required before mapping [10].

4.2 Impact of Cobot Development

Furthermore, cobots make a lot of decisions in real time, and the search space might be quite big. This necessitates traversal of vast knowledge graphs, which necessitates processing power, a dependable network, and unique software structures. However, current advancements in technologies like as linked data, parallel processing, edge computing, and distributed artificial intelligence enable cobots to make optimal decisions, resulting in robust and efficient execution.

The difficulties of deploying cobots at scale Massive deployments of any new technology are a chicken-and-egg dilemma, as industries must establish use cases for cobots. All robotic automation in the past has been set up and fine-tuned during the design stage. In the ideal instance, it has been modified at run-time using a data-driven strategy. Cobots provide process designers the chance to train cobots to carry out tasks and actively grow at run-time, allowing for advances through artificial intelligence. The technology is available, but in order to achieve enormous deployments at scale, the use cases must be established at scale.

A problem with the market adoption of cobots is that insufficient technological development makes it difficult. Technology used in cobots comprises hardware design, sensors, actuators, effective information processing, video processing, planning, and several artificial intelligence-related domains, as well as technologies that provide safety, predictability, and the solution's security [11].

- **Trust:** When a technology becomes reliable, it spreads rapidly. People put tape on microphones or laptop cameras when they don't trust their device or programme. Similarly, we would be hesitant to engage with industrial robots if we did not trust them.
- **Reliability:** The difficulties of deploying cobots at scale massive deployments of any new technology are a chicken-and-egg dilemma, as industries must establish use cases for cobots. Although the technology is already in place, large-scale use cases still need to be developed before they can be deployed.
- **Safety:** Insufficient technological maturity is a barrier to cobot market deployment. Cobot technology encompasses hardware design, sensors and actuators, efficient information processing, video processing, planning, and a variety of disciplines from artificial intelligence landscapes, as well as technologies that ensure the solution's safety, predictability, and security.

5. Merits & Demerits of Cobots

According to ABI Research (global technology intelligence firm) , the worldwide cobot market is expected to grow at a CAGR of 32.5% from USD 600 million in 2021 to USD 8 billion in 2030. To lower costs, shorten time-to-market, and meet expanding customer demands, modern production necessitates excellent human-machine collaboration. Here's how cobots can help manufacturing companies [8].

Aspect	Merits (Advantages)	Demerits (Disadvantages)
Safety	- Designed to work alongside humans, reducing the risk of injury.	- May still pose some level of risk if not properly programmed or maintained.
Productivity	- Enhances productivity by automating repetitive and mundane tasks.	- Initial setup and programming may require time and expertise.
Flexibility	- Easy to program and reprogram for different tasks and workflows.	- Limited payload and speed compared to traditional industrial robots.

Collaboration	- Can work in close proximity with humans, fostering collaboration.	- Limited payload capacity compared to traditional robots.
Cost	- Generally more affordable than traditional industrial robots.	- Upfront costs can still be high for small businesses or startups.
Ease of Use	- Intuitive and user-friendly programming interfaces.	- Requires training and skilled personnel for programming and maintenance.
Space Requirement	- Compact and can operate in small workspaces.	- May require additional space for safety measures and peripheral equipment.
Adaptability	- Easily adaptable to changing production needs.	- May require upgrades or modifications to handle new tasks.
Integration	- Compatible with existing systems and machinery.	- Integration into existing processes may require customization and adjustments.
Maintenance	- Generally low maintenance compared to traditional robots.	- Specialized maintenance and occasional downtime for updates and repairs.

It's important to note that the advantages and disadvantages of cobots can vary based on specific use cases, industries, and applications. Additionally, advancements in technology may address some of the demerits over time.

6. Application of Cobots in Apparel Industry

The low entrance threshold of a cobot's cell makes it appealing. The investment is cheaper than that of a robot cell. Cobot is perfect for obtaining experience in Automation and even programming knowledge are not required. For instance, many products are relatively inexpensive in the assembly and packaging industry. Even in a clean working environment where the Picking and placement are the only acts that cobot can perform very well. However, the lack of adaptability remains an issue. It paints a picture of future cyber-physical operations that merge robots, cobots, and people to maximize productivity and quality, while minimizing overall costs. Cobot performance and learning may be enhanced using AI and machine vision. A variety of functions are offered by intelligent cobot vision systems, including item location and identification, barcode and totem interpretation, pattern matching, and colour recognition. The cobot may be instructed in new procedures and guided from position to position using hand gestures enabled by the vision system. In other instances, machine operators may rapidly and effectively train cobots utilizing a tablet computer and a drag-and-drop flowchart-based approach. Cobots can be adapted to a variety of production procedures, such as machine tending, screwdriving, and dispensing. CNC (computer numerical control) machines, stamping and punch presses, various cutting machines, and injection molding stations are among the machine tending tasks where cobots can relieve people from repetitive and potentially dangerous activities. Inspecting finished parts or products is another area where cobots with machine vision can excel. If the part is complex, a thorough inspection may require high-resolution images from various angles requiring the coordination of multiple stationary cameras. Alternatively, a cobot with a single camera can identify the part being inspected and move around the part accordingly, capturing all the needed images for a complete visual inspection [14].

7. Future Scenarios – Collaboration of Man and Machine

Industry 4.0 opened the way for data-driven technologies like IoT, cyber-physical systems, wearables, AR, cloud computing, artificial intelligence, cognitive computing, and so on to power automation and smart manufacturing. Though Industry 4.0's only goal is to enhance process efficiency through physical and digital integration, it inadvertently overlooks the importance of human value in process optimization. By merging the responsibilities of mechanical components and human employees in manufacturing, Industry 5.0 refocuses on human value. As a result, cobots will form the fundamental core of the next wave of the industrial revolution, known as Industry 5.0. According to Universal Robots of Denmark, cobots are at the core of Industry 5.0. Cobots may be utilized as a plug-and-play solution in a wide range of manufacturing and industrial processes, including automobile production, food processing, chemical plants, medical devices, and kits [13].

However, present technologies are simply a first step in the field of human-robot interaction. As Artificial Intelligence research advances, the programming of Cobots will most likely become considerably simpler, if not obsolete, in the future. Cobots may revamp a company's whole manufacturing process "A cooperative robot" may impact several processes in an appropriate manner and manage a gain in efficiency of at least 30 to 40%." The Increased production, but also by a reduction in worker and sick leave is, nonetheless, It is impossible to determine the precise amount of efficiency boost obtained by cobots because might differ widely from one firm to the next and from one sector to the next.

"Automation and the cost of robotic technology might soon be comparable with low-wage jobs." The ramifications for garment assembly employees if machines replace them on a broadscale, the implications for industry and underdeveloped countries would be significant. As the world's population grows to an anticipated 9 billion people by 2030, the garment industry is predicted to quadruple in scale to a \$4.4 trillion enterprise with regional manufacturing clusters growing to new consumer markets. Just as in past industrial revolutions, when factory owners embraced new technologies, technology to gain a competitive edge in their businesses, it is incumbent on today's businesses to invest in the education of tomorrow's workforce."

Cobots will complement intelligent decision-making since they work well with people in a safesetting. Boost the market for high-quality products, allow for mass customization and personalization reduce production costs, create new job titles (for example, Chief Robotics Officer), and increase virtual schooling to take use of collaborative robots [14].

- Service providers must be prepared to deliver consistent, differentiated quality of service via their networks. Because application safety and predictability requirements (in this example, cobots) propagate requirements on network infrastructure, service providers will need to provide a specific quality of service in safety-critical scenarios.
- Technology suppliers will need to guarantee that the systems are trustworthy in terms of predictability, security, and safety. They must also guarantee that rules and standards are followed.
- As this technology evolves, businesses will need to find use cases that profit from human-robot collaboration.

8. Conclusion

In conclusion, a cobot is particularly well suited as an entry-level automation model for businesses that have minimal expertise with technology and robotics and/or have limited budgets. The potential of using without safety boundaries, a robotic workplace may be tempted to be completely utilized. Products that are automated in order to reduce installation space as well as the expenses of safety barriers. It is feasible in some circumstances to be content with the cobot's poorer machine efficiency and dearth of features—features that a loading robot might in fact provide. Everything is based on how the business is run. But sooner or later, businesses in the machining sector frequently make the move to a loading robot.

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